

Syntactic-Semantic Structure of Twila Paris' Song "the Joy of the Lord": A Discourse Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the syntactic and semantic structure of Twila Paris' song titled "The Joy of the Lord." The study utilized discourse analysis exploring the data through the immediate constituent of the sentence and semantic analysis such as the function and notion of the idea expressed, and the sentence transforms. The findings show that the majority of the sentence in the song is simple sentences. The study reveals the following functions of sentences: describing something, describing someone, and declaring something. The notions are expressing someone's strength, upholding God, declaring God's mercy and grace, declaring not to waive someone's faith, and describing someone strong. The song has sentences transformed with nominative, possessive, and objective focus. This result indicates that teachers can engage their students in syntactic and semantic analysis that will help students enhance their linguistic awareness and appreciation and deepen their understanding of the song.

Subject Area

Teaching

Keywords: *discourse analysis, function, immediate Constituent Analysis, notion, Syntactic Analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

Language is an essential tool for communication. It cannot be separated from the human being. People use language to express feelings and emotions, share an idea or opinions, and also criticize. Due to these undeniable facts, people realize the importance of language in their daily life. People use language as the media in communication either in oral or written forms. Here, the language used ought to be meaningful and understandable to avoid misunderstanding and misinterpretation.

Understanding language from different perspectives depends on the situation and context in which the communication transpires. Language is studied in order to see the connection of the different parts of the text especially in yielding meaning of any literary work such as poetry and

songs. Furthermore, language in communication is meaningful when it is well-arranged and relevant to the context surrounding the communication.

In linguistics, the study of the sentence of languages is syntax. Gleason (2019) defines syntax as the principles of the arrangement of the construction formed by the process of derivation and inflection (word) into larger constructions of various kinds. Further, Hodge (2019) postulates that syntax concerns the discovery of basic sentence types with the description or the possible substitutions for each element of the basic types. Moreover, Syntax is the way words or terms are joined to form clauses, phrases, or sentences. Word order plays an essential role in determining the meaning of any song or poetry. Wallace et al. (2014) mention that the logical presentation of thought in syntax provides an excellent means to study any literary work like a song or a poem.

Hence, the researcher was motivated in conducting a syntactic-semantic analysis of the select sentences excerpted from a song. This work is concerned with the analysis of the use of words in a song in order to enhance the effective transfer of the message conveyed. As a kind of written text, a song has a specific structure and composition in order to make the reader understand the message conveyed. The structure and composition studied in a song will demonstrate and give a clearer understanding to the students of how sentences are constructed and interpreted into different meanings.

This study, therefore, deals with the analysis of the structure of a sentence and the sentence transformation generated from sentences excerpted from a song. The structure of a sentence must be mastered by the second language specifically English so that the learner would be able to construct sentences accurately following the linearity of constituents.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

This investigation assumes that the select sentences excerpted from the song “The Joy of the Lord” by Twila Paris reveal surface and deep structure in linearity. This research analysis was basically anchored on the theory of Noam Chomsky’s Syntactic structure which introduces the idea of generative-transformational grammar. It is basically a theory to understand the processing of grammatical knowledge in the human brain. Transformational grammar refers to “a form of language analysis that establishes a relationship with the different elements in the sentence of a language and makes use of rules or transformations to recognize these relationships.” (Nordquist,2019).

Furthermore, Hurley (2018) illustrates this theory as describing a language with the help of transformational rules. It involves logical reasoning to understand fully the meaning of the selected words. Transformational grammar employs most of the linguistic tools such as syntax and context to explore the possible meanings of words. In generative transformational grammar theory, phrase structure rules illustrate mathematically our knowledge of how the basic units of a sentence are assembled.

This linguistic research analyses the surface and deep structure of the five select sentences. Specifically, the study answers the following sub-problems:

1. How do the Immediate Constituents construct the surface structures of the sentence?
2. What functions do the sentences reveal?
3. What motives are revealed by the sentences?

4. How are the sentence transformations constructed?

The findings of the linguistic research analysis would provide effective feedback and substantial information to the following persons: a) the results of the research work may be beneficial to the curriculum designers in the implementation of the linguistic research program for the enhancement of the students' linguistic competence; b) the findings of the study may provide input to the Linguistic teachers which may result in the design of activities, teaching techniques and strategies in helping, promoting and enhancing student's linguistic skills; and c) the study may give awareness to the students of English as the second language of the linguistic features of the songs.

The scope of the study is focused on the five select sentences excerpted from the song "The Joy of the Lord" by Twila Paris. The study is limited within the parameters of the Immediate Constituent Analysis of the five sentences collected, the functions revealed in the sentences, the notion revealed in the sentences and the sentence transforms of the five sentences.

METHODOLOGY OF THE LINGUISTIC RESEARCH

Linguistic Research Design

The method used in this study is discourse analysis, specifically, structural analysis and description of constituents. The structural analysis involves the immediate constituent and the semantic components of the sentences. The description of constituents involves the transformation of sentences according to case.

Sources of Data

The select song titled "The Joy of the Lord" by Twila Paris is the main source of the data where the five select model sentences are excerpted.

Data-generating Process

Analyzed in this study was the poem or song of Twila Paris, "The joy of the Lord." The syntactic-semantic analysis of the poem or song is organized into four phases:

Phase one: Immediate Constituent Analysis. This phase is employed by identifying the syntactic structure of sentences or analyzing the surface structure of the sentences.

Phase two: Function or Speech Acts analysis. In this phase, the function or Speech act employed in the sentences is analyzed.

Phase three: Notions or Idea Expressed. In this phase, the analysis is done by identifying the notion or idea expressed in each sentence.

Phase four: Sentence Transforms. In this phase, sentence transform is constructed using several syntactic structures of the same meaning such as nominative focus, possessive focus, and objective focus

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussions focusing on the analytical data derived from the linguistic analysis of the select five sentences excerpted from Twila Paris' song "The Joy of the Lord".

The data follows the following sentences as outlined below:

I. Sentence One: *The Joy of the Lord will be my strength.*

A. Immediate Constituent Analysis:

The Joy of the Lord will be my strength
D + N + PREP + D + N + AUX + V + D + N

B. Function: instrument+ action + describing something

C. Notion: expressing someone's strength.

D. Sentence Transforms

1. The joy of the Lord will give me strength. (Nominative Focus)

2. The Lord's joy will be my strength. (Possessive Focus)

3. The joy of the Lord will have been my strength. (Objective Focus).

II. Sentence Two: *He will uphold me all of my days.*

A. Immediate Constituent Analysis:

He will uphold me all of my days.
PRON + AUX + V + PRON + ADJ + PREP + D + N

B. Function: doer+ action + receiver + adverb/ describing someone

C. Notion: upholding God

D. Sentence Transforms:

1. The Lord will uphold me all the days. (Nominative Focus)

2. My days will be upheld by the Lord. (Possessive Focus)

3. I will be upheld by the Lord all the days. (Objective Focus)

III. Sentence Three: *I am surrounded by mercy and grace.*

A. Immediate Constituent Analysis:

I am surrounded by mercy and grace.
PRON + AUX + V + PREP + N + CONJ + N

B. Function: doer+ action + object of preposition+ describing someone

C. Notion: declaring God's mercy and grace

D. Sentence Transforms:

1. God surrounded me with His mercy and grace. (Nominative Focus)

2. God's mercy and love surrounded me. (Possessive Focus)

3. I have been surrounded by God's mercy and grace. (Objective Focus)

IV. Sentence Four: *I will not waiver, walking by faith.*

A. Immediate Constituent Analysis:

I will not waiver, walking by faith.
PRON + AUX + ADV + V + V + PREP + N

B. Function: doer+ action + object of preposition/ declaring something

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- C. Notion: declaring not to waive someone's faith
 - D. Sentence Transforms:
 1. I walk by faith and never waive it. (Nominative Focus)
 2. My faithfulness to the Lord will not be waived. (Possessive Focus)
 3. Faith will have not be waived by me. (Objective Focus)
 - V. Sentence Five: *He will be strong to deliver me safe.*
 - A. Immediate Constituent Analysis:

He will be strong to deliver me safe.

PRON + AUX + V + V + INF + PRON + ADJ

- B. Function: doer+ action + describing someone
- C. Notion: describing someone strong
- D. Sentence Transforms:
 1. The Lord has the strength to deliver me safely. (Nominative Focus)
 2. The Lord's strength will deliver me safely. (Possessive Focus)
 3. The strength of the Lord will have delivered me safely. (Objective Focus)

FINDINGS

The following results were disclosed after analyzing the data gathered and hereby summarized:

The Immediate Constituent Analysis that constructs the surface structure of the sentence are as follows: 1) Sentence 1 is a simple sentence which is made up of the following constituents: determiner, noun, preposition, and auxiliary verb; 2) Sentence 2 is a simple sentence which is made up of the following constituents: pronoun, adjective, preposition, determiner, verb and noun; 3) Sentence 3 is a simple sentence which is made up of the following constituents: pronoun, auxiliary verb, preposition, conjunction and noun; 4) Sentence 4 is a simple sentence which is made up of the following constituents: pronoun, auxiliary verb, adverb, preposition, noun, and verb; and Sentence 5 is a simple sentence which is made up of the following constituents: pronoun, adjective, infinitive, auxiliary verb, and verb.

The five sentences reveal the following functions: describing something, describing someone, and declaring something. The five sentences reveal the following notions: expressing someone's strength, upholding God, declaring God's mercy and grace, declaring not to waive someone's faith, and describing someone's strong. The five sentences construct three-sentence transforms with nominative focus, five-sentence transforms with five possessive focus and five-sentence transforms with objective focus.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings it has been concluded that the five select sentences excerpted from the song "The Joy of the Lord" by Twila Paris reveal surface and deep structure in linearity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. The language teachers of English may conduct the Immediate Constituent Analysis activity so that the language learners of English may know the different constituents that could make up the surface structure of a sentence.

2. The language teachers of English may emphasize the importance of identifying the function of the utterance by letting the language learners of English determine the functions of sentences which they may come across within daily conversation so that these learners may notice that every utterance that a person throws at his/her interlocutor is done because of his intention or purpose.

3. The language teachers of English may implore Integrative teaching strategies infusing literary devices to facilitate effective learning in grammar; engaging their students in a different kind of analysis like immediate constituent analysis to allow students to explore and apply their linguistic skills.; and using different linguistic activities integrating literary devices to enhance the linguistic skills of the students.

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Practices on Work-Related Values of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS) Teaching Personnel: Its Cultural Values Assessment

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the work-related values practices of the elementary and secondary teaching personnel of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS) vis-à-vis its cultural value assessment. The participants of the study were the 280 randomly selected elementary and secondary teachers in all BUACS' member schools during the school year 2018-2019. The research questionnaire of Schwartz, et al. (2001) specifically on the work-related values dimension served as the data gathering instrument. Mean and standard deviation revealed that both the elementary and the secondary teaching personnel of BUACS member schools practiced to a great extent their work-related values.

Subject Area

Values Assessment

Keywords: *Work-related values, Cultural Values Assessment*

INTRODUCTION

Work values are generalized beliefs about the desired status of different aspects of work, such as working conditions and outcomes such as accomplishments (Lyons et al., 2010). Stated differently, work values represent evaluative standards and goals in the organizational context (Froese & Xiao, 2012). It can be defined as those qualities that people desire from their work which affect between a corresponding need and satisfaction. These values are considered evaluative standards relating to work or the work environment by which individuals discuss what is 'right' or assess the importance of preferences.

The Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS) is a faith-based institutions where belief in God is part of everyday environment. Daily prayers and spiritual formation enriched the School's cultural values by regular attendance in masses and other religious activities. Inspirational

words and images are present throughout the schools giving frequent reminders of God's message for the school's stakeholders. These experiences give the teaching personnel a chance to understand the beliefs, purposes, issues and practices of the Catholic faith, with a firm sense of values and faith. These practices are reflected in their work ethics with or without being conscious about these. Eventually, these teaching personnel serve as model for the students to move out into the world as more humane and service-oriented.

According to Ren, (2010) employees' effort is the number of attentional resources that an employee dedicates to a job/task. Motivating employees to increase their work effort to achieve organizational goals is an important issue for managers as employees' organizational duties have become less routinized and defined, organizations increasingly seek to retain individuals who uphold high levels of work effort on their own.

Determining the work values of every employee is an important part of the organization's growth. According to Hofstede (2001), work values are significant for two different reasons. First, they are an excellent measure of culture in that they are shaped more by sociological and cultural factors than individual psychological differences. Secondly, the work values of an organization's employees will affect the organization in many ways, from conflict resolution, to its ability to change, to communication, to employee's motivation.

Work values occupy a specific domain within the context of people's lives. They govern the importance placed on work and work-related aspects by individuals and groups of people within the context of the entirety of their lives. Research on work values indicates that such values are derived from the same basic value systems which guide individual through the various facets of their lives. In this sense, they are a specific subset of general life values; and so, are influenced by intrinsic and extrinsic factors.

The construct of work values is associated with work related concepts including: attitudes (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1972); job satisfaction (Locke, 1976); employee turnover (Steers & Mowday, 1981); organizational 'fit' (Rounds, Dawis & Lofquist, 1987); motivation (Locke, 1991); career choice (Judge & Bretz, 1992); organizational commitment (Meyer, Irving, & Allen, 1998); team dynamics (Dose & Klimoski, 1999); and organizational citizenship behavior (Feather & Rauter, 2004). From these constructs emerged the notion of 'work values and the understanding that such values are relevant and important to an individual's work and working life.

As with general values, work values act as the criteria individuals utilize in making and enacting work-related choices. Their goals and behaviors are influenced by work values. Previous research shows that work values and general values are distinct but related concepts (Sagie & Elizur, 1996) which work values are being derived from broader general values. Moving beyond the idea of work values as the foundation for important and much-used theories of motivation, work values in and of themselves have important implications for the organization.

Work values can explain differences in individual performance and predict job satisfaction to develop a committed workforce and to prepare the organization to be able to function during period of change. In addition, understanding employee's work values has been found to aid negotiation (Graham, Mintu, & Rodgers, 1994), to assist in developing effective reward system (Matic, JL 2008); to affect leadership and management style and to facilitate communication and organization performance.

Recognizing the importance of knowing the work-related values practiced by the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS) would be of great help to the administrators, employees, students of every member school and the community. It is important that the work values of the teaching personnel are aligned with those reflected by the institution for productivity, job satisfaction, and creative potentials.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study examined the work-related values practiced by the teaching personnel of Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS) vis-à-vis its cultural assessment for the school year, 2018-2019.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of practice on the work-related values of the elementary and secondary teaching personnel of Bukidnon Association of Catholics Schools (BUACS)?
2. What is the cultural value assessment on the work-related values practiced by the elementary and secondary teaching personnel of the Bukidnon Association of Catholics Schools (BUACS)?

METHODOLOGY

Twenty-six member schools of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS) participated in the study during the school year 2018-2019. These schools are in the northern and southern parts of Bukidnon. The 26 member schools of BUACS are categorized into three groups according to the number of enrollees. Schools with 200-300 enrollees are classified as small schools; those with 301-500 enrollees are medium schools and those with 501 or more enrollees are categorized as big schools.

The member schools of Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS) are distributed to the three congressional districts in the Province of Bukidnon. There are six (6) members schools located in District 1 is the municipalities of Bukidnon, namely: Holy Cross High School, Camp Philips, Manolo Fortich Bukidnon, Pangantucan Community High School, in Pangantucan Bukidnon, Pilar High School, in Kisolon, Sumilao Bukidnon, Saint Joseph and Saint Therese High School in Talakag Bukidnon and San Isidro High School, Malipayon, Pangantucan Bukidnon.

Twelve (12) member schools are located in District 2 in the province of Bukidnon, namely: Father Leoni Memorial High School in Cabanglasan, Good Council High School in Mailag Valencia City, Sacred Heart Academy, in Dagatkidavao, Valencia City, Saint Joseph High School, Zamboanguita, Malaybalay City, Saint Michael High School in Linabo, Malaybaslay City, San Augustine Institute of Technology in Valencia City, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, San Jose High School in Laligan, Valencia City, Santo Niño High School in Valencia City, and Xavier de Kibangay High School, in Kibangay Lantapan Bukidnon, while one member school is located outside the congressional district of Bukidnon. It is situated in the first district Lanao del Sur, the La Purisima High School in Wao, Lanao del Sur.

Lastly, there are six (6) members school located in the third District of Bukidnon, namely: Loyola High School in Don Carlos Bukidnon, Nuestra Señora del Pilar High School in Quezon Bukidnon, Our Lady of Fatima High School in Dagumbaan, Maramag Bukidnon, San Andres High

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School in Maramag Bukidnon, Stella Matutina High School in Kibawe Bukidnon and Xavier de Damulog High School in Damulog Bukidnon.

The instrument was adopted from the cultural values dimensions of Schwartz, et al, (2001) with modifications to suit the present study. The work-related dimension has 10 indicators and these were utilized to assess the BUACS personnel's work values. The researcher followed proper protocol in the conduct of the study, by asking permission from the heads of the institutions and personally conducted the survey, then tabulated and analyzed the results based from the criteria set in the study.

FINDINGS

Work related values of the elementary teaching personnel of the teaching personnel of the Bukidnon Association of Catholics Schools

Table 1 presents the extent of the practice of work-related values of the teaching personnel of the member schools of Bukidnon Association of Catholics Schools. In general, the elementary teaching personnel of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic School practiced to a great extent their work-related values. The result shows that Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools' elementary school teachers evidently manifested to a great extent the three indicators, namely: (1) seeks to improve proficiency and efficiency in a task/ in an assignment, (2) participates in school and other related activities and (3) accepts/adjusts to other assignments/functions. This result means that work related values are natural among the elementary school teachers of the association and practice the work values at all times. This result implies that the elementary teachers have the motivation and the desire to do their responsibility and the assigned task. As observed, despite the many tasks the teachers faced, they still accomplished these tasks efficiently. The teachers demonstrate competence and capacity in doing their classroom and/or office responsibilities to meet the deadline with accuracy and quality of output to a great extent.

Table 1.

Extent of the practice on work related values of the elementary teaching personnel of the Bukidnon Association of Catholics Schools

Indicators	Mean	S.D.	Qualifying Description
Seeks to improve proficiency and efficiency in a task/ in an assignment	4.44	0.50	Great extent
Participates in school and other related activities	4.36	072	Great extent
Accepts/adjusts to other assignments/functions	4.36	0.63	Great extent
Knows how to prioritize his/her task	4.32	0.58	Great extent
Demonstrates being a team player	4.30	0.74	Great extent
Cooperates with organizational policies, practices, And guidelines	4.27	0.74	Great extent
Makes himself/herself available for planning and consultation	4.24	0.68	Great extent
Delivers/does the task with quality	4.21	0.78	Great extent
Demonstrate his/her competence and capacity in doing his/her office /classroom responsibilities	4.13	0.71	Great extent
Meets deadlines with accuracy and quality of output	4.00	0.75	Great extent
OVERALL	4.25	0.51	Great extent

According to Josephine Pryce (2014) in her journal entitled “*Work Values: Formidable Domain within the Context of People’s Lives*,” work values occupy a specific domain within the context of people's lives. They govern the important place on work and work-related aspects by individuals (and groups of people) within the context of the entirety of their lives. Research on work values indicates that such values are derived from the same basic value systems which guide individuals through the various facets of their lives. In this sense, they are a specific subset of general life values. These values are influenced by intrinsic and extrinsic factors. The literature contends that factors such as demographics, nationality, organizations and occupation have a strong impact on work values (Schwartz, 1995).

The article also suggests that there are ‘better’ and ‘not so good’ work values, e.g., the idea of the Protestant work ethic. In developing this article, the contention is to examine how the notion of ‘work values’ is explored in the literature and ascertain how the work values of ordinary individuals illustrates the differences and dominance of work values. As part of a bigger research project, this article could add to the understanding of the existence of a hierarchy and domination of work values among individuals and between groups of people; and, whether such understanding can lead to minimization of dominance of one set of work values over another and so effect greater harmonization specifically in workplaces and among workforces. It is argued that such knowledge can assist in ascertaining how to minimize or maximize dominance of one set of work values over another so as to improve working lives and create more sustainable workforces and harmonious workplaces.

Extent of the practice of the work-related values dimension of the secondary teaching personnel of the Bukidnon Association of Catholics Schools

Table 2 presents the extent the secondary teaching personnel of Bukidnon Association of Catholics Schools practice the work-related values. The over-all result shows that the secondary teaching personnel of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS) displayed to a great extent the work related values. The result shows that the secondary school teaching personnel practice at all times the work-related values like participate in school and other related activities and cooperate with organizational policies, practices, and guidelines. This implies that dedication and seriousness of the teachers in the work assigned were demonstrated. The secondary teaching personnel give their best in imparting knowledge to their students, except that at some point they were not able to meet deadlines with accuracy and quality of output.

Table 2.

Extent of the practice of the work-related values dimension of the secondary teaching personnel of the Bukidnon Association of Catholics Schools

Indicators	Mean	S.D.	Qualifying Description
Participates in school and other related activities	4.46	.65	Great extent
Cooperates with organizational policies, practices, And guidelines	4.43	.59	Great extent
Demonstrate his/her competence and capacity in doing his/her office /classroom responsibilities	4.43	.56	Great extent
Seeks to improve proficiency and efficiency in a task/ in an assignment	4.42	.62	Great extent
Accepts/adjusts to other assignments/functions	4.40	.59	Great extent
Knows how to prioritize his/her task	4.39	.58	Great extent
Makes himself/herself available for planning and consultation	4.36	.66	Great extent
Demonstrates being a team player	4.35	.64	Great extent
Delivers/does the task with quality	4.31	.59	Great extent
Meets deadlines with accuracy and quality of output	4.17	.62	Moderate extent
OVERALL	4.37	.45	Great extent

In Super et al. (1995) description of work values, they emphasized the various motivators that drive the individual to work. Work values are regarded as values that are extrinsic and intrinsic to work satisfaction and this may be seen as the by-product or outcomes of work and those which men and women seek in their work activity.

The individual upholds an evaluative disposition or inclination regarding work in general. Van Plesten, (1986) cited work values as the orientation an individual holds in general. Zytowski, (1970) described work values as a set of concepts which mediates between a person's affective orientation and classes of external objects offering similar satisfaction. Wollack, (1971) described work values as an index of a person's attitude towards work in general rather than his feelings about a specific job. Work values demonstrate the usefulness or general worth that a person assigns to some behavior or conception of work (e.g. Physical effort and length of time on task/job) and non-work activities (e.g. leisure, benefits, and rewards). To summarize, it could be said that work related values are indicative of an individual's (workers) inner attitude or way of thinking towards his work, on condition that it does not merely apply to his own post or a certain task, but rather to work in general.

Cultural Values Assessment on the work-related values of the elementary teaching personnel of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools

Table 3 presents the cultural values assessment on the work-related values of the elementary teaching personnel of Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools. It shows that the cultural value assessment in their work-related values proves that majority of the elementary teaching personnel practiced at all times in dealing with their responsibilities to the students, parents and the school. They practice their work-related values to a great extent except for items number 5 & 7 which is to a moderate extent or practiced most of the time.

Table 3.
Cultural Values Assessment on the work-related values of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools' elementary teaching personnel

Indicators	N	Mean	Qualifying Description
Seeks to improve proficiency and efficiency in a task/ in an assignment	36	4.44	Great extent
Participates in school and other related activities	36	4.36	Great extent
Accepts/adjusts to other assignments/functions	36	4.36	Great extent
Knows how to prioritize his/her task	37	4.32	Great extent
Demonstrates being a team player	36	4.31	Great extent
Cooperates with organizational policies, practices, And guidelines	36	4.28	Great extent
Makes himself/herself available for planning and consultation	37	4.24	Great extent
Delivers/does the task with quality	37	4.22	Great extent
Demonstrate his/her competence and capacity in doing his/her office /classroom responsibilities	37	4.14	Moderate extent
Meets deadlines with accuracy and quality of output	36	4.00	Moderate extent
WRV Average	37	4.26	Great extent

According to Ali & Panatik (2013), in their work relationship between *Work Values and Work-Related Attitude: The Role of Social Support as Moderator*, work values are one of the subsets of overall human values. Work values act as common values that are always being discussed relating to the employee's development and achievement in their workplace. In the organization, work values can function as evaluative standards that people use to interpret their work experiences and determine the meaning that individuals attribute to work, jobs, organizations, specific events and conditions. The impact of work values on work-related attitudes become an interesting topic among researchers. Based on the review of the previous research in this area, most of the researchers have their own understanding and definition to explain work values among employees in the organization.

It is highlighted that there are fifteen dimensions of work values that had been investigated based on the *Work Values Inventory* which are altruism, aesthetics, creativity, intellectual stimulation, achievement, independence, prestige, management, economic returns, security, surrounding, supervisory relations, association, way of life, and lastly is variety. Some researchers divided these fifteen dimensions of work values into three categories, which are intrinsic (terminal values), extrinsic (instrumental values) and concomitant values (Robinson & Betz, 2008). However, some of the researchers argued that there are only two common types of work values among employees, which are intrinsic and extrinsic work values (Chin-Chih, 2006).

Cultural Values Assessment on the work-related values of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools' secondary teaching personnel

Table 4 presents the cultural values assessment on the work-related values of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools' secondary teaching personnel. The result shows that majority of the respondents of the study says that their work-related values are practiced most of the time which is evident in the overall mean at 4.37 described to a great extent. It also implies that in terms of cultural values assessment there are shared common characteristics as manifested in the result of the study.

Table 4.

Cultural Values Assessment on work related values of the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools' secondary teaching personnel

Indicators	N	Mean	Qualifying Description
Participates in school and other related activities	240	4.46	Great extent
Demonstrate his/her competence and capacity in doing his/her office classroom responsibilities	242	4.43	Great extent
Cooperates with organizational policies, practices, And guidelines	240	4.43	Great extent
Seeks to improve proficiency and efficiency in a task/ in an assignment	240	4.42	Great extent
Accepts/adjusts to other assignments/functions	242	4.40	Great extent
Knows how to prioritize his/her task	239	4.39	Great extent
Makes himself/herself available for planning and consultation	242	4.36	Great extent
Demonstrates being a team player	239	4.35	Great extent
Delivers/does the task with quality	242	4.31	Great extent
Meets deadlines with accuracy and quality of output	241	4.17	Moderate extent
WRV Average	242	4.37	Great extent

The mean per indicator of the work-related values as assessed by the respondents of the study has little difference which is generally described to a *great extent*, except for indicator 7 which has a mean of 4.17 described to *moderate extent* or practiced most of the time. Generally, the teachers from the member schools of the BUACS really demonstrate the indicators pointed on the work-related values expected of the teachers.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study the elementary and secondary teaching personnel of the BUACS practiced the work-related values to a *great extent*. They are motivated to perform the tasks under this dimension. The personnel seek to improve proficiency and efficiency in a task, participate in school and other related activities, accept/adjust to other assignments/functions. It could be deduced that the BUACS teaching personnel have demonstrated the intrinsic and extrinsic work values in their respective schools, hence BUACS administration have to strengthen these values among its personnel for them to continue to practice their profession and create more impact among the stakeholders especially the learners.

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